

Predicting the Value of the Next Planck Constant – 8T

O Manor

August 14, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series and in particular the term of Electro-magnetism and the photon which is associated with net variation element $N_V = +(5)$ it is possible to predict the value of the next Planck constant, that is by the ratio of the net variations of the next element in the series. It should be 1.4 larger than the original Planck constant.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration in page two.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. The paper main point is to provide a theoretical prediction regarding the fourth interaction. Since from measurement we know the value of the Planck constant, and in our theory, it is associated with the net variation element of the third coupling term; we can predict the next value of the Planck constant for the fourth coupling term based on the ratio of the net variation of the two coupling terms, as they are the discrete amounts which get emitted or absorbed into the lepton.

$$\hbar \rightarrow +5$$

Define the next Planck constant as:

$$\hbar_n \rightarrow +7$$

$$\frac{\hbar_n}{\hbar} = 1.4$$

In agreement with what we expect, as each net variation is larger than the preceding, now we can take the actual value of the Planck constant and multiply by the ratio to reach the exact prediction – the next Planck Constant should be 1.4 larger than the original Planck is and stand as:

$$9.27649806 \times 10^{-34} \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg /s}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Okad